

Sex Determination and Barcoding by ISSR Method in Rattan Jernang (*Daemonorops draco*) : A Review

Alivia Zulkarnain (2110422037) – Genetic and Biomolecular Laboratory, Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Andalas University, Padang

Daemonorops is a genus of rattan palms. The genus consists of 115 species, but only 12 of which produce resin known as dragon's blood palm. *Daemonorops draco* (Willd.) Blume is a species that produces the most resin of high economic value, because of its larger fruits and longer in fructescences. *Daemonorops draco* is usually found in Sumatra (Jambi, Riau, and Bengkulu) and Kalimantan. *Daemonorops draco* resin can be internally processed in the human body to improve blood circulation, improve tissue regeneration, cure sprains, ulcers, control bleeding, and relieve pain (Asra et al., 2014). Jernang rattan which grows in peaty soil, has the characteristics of a single stem or not in clumps, short fruit stalks, grows well in areas with a litter thickness of up to 30 cm to 50 cm, has the main root of one fruit which can reach 5 meters in length, the rest are short roots in a zigzag position. It is difficult to propagate plants because the fruit is always harvested when it is still young or half the size of the old fruit or ripe fruit, when young the Jernang Rattan fruit has a high resin content when compared to the old fruit. This is different from the Jernang Rattan in Jambi which is harvested when the fruit is old or almost ripe Click or tap here to enter text.. Lately, some research about *Daemonorops draco* is about the genetic diversity, morphology, potential, population and habitat, sex ratio, etc. Meanwhile, research on determination and barcoding sex in *Daemonorops draco* has never been carried out before. Studies on the sex ratio of Jernang (*D. draco*) in both natural and cultivated populations have never been carried out. It is very important to study the sex ratio of Jernang to find out what the sex ratio of Jernang is in both natural and cultivated habitats. Understanding the sex ratio of Jernang will be useful in the development of seed gardens to ensure more efficient seed production for Jernang cultivation in the future (Asra et al., 2012).

Jernang rattan is a cultivated plant that has socio-cultural value for local communities and can be developed as a source of income for families. Apart from that, jernang rattan is also used as industrial raw material, medicine and natural dye which can be developed as a product for the pharmaceutical industry, raw material for herbal medicine and other industries. Demand for jernang is increasing every year. Cultivation of Jernang rattan is expected to be one of the efforts to ensure the preservation of Jernang rattan, whose existence is increasingly limited, and is expected to play a role in increasing people's income (Asra et al., 2021). The potential for rattan to produce jernang can be seen from its species density value. The density of a species is determined by environmental factors, namely the conditions where it grows, competition and relationships with other species. The density of a species is determined by environmental factors, namely the conditions in which it grows, competition with other species and its relationship with other species. Density is largely determined by the distribution of a species and the distribution itself is determined by the availability of dispersal agents in the environment, such as water, animals, wind, etc (Wahyudi & Syasri Jannetta, 2011).

In Indonesia there are 84 species of the *Daemonorops* genus, then it has been increased to 113, and the latest data was 115 types (Rustiarni et al., 2004). However, of the 115 types of *Daemonorops*, only 12 types produce jernang resin, namely *D. didymophylla*, *D. draco*, *D. draconsellus*, *Daemonorops matleyi*, *Daemonorops micracantha*, *Daemonorops melanochaetes*, *Daemonorops longipes*, *Daemonorops acehensis*, *Daemonorops branchystachys*, *Daemonorops dransfieldii*, *Daemonorops maculata*, and *Daemonorops cyberutensis*. Meanwhile, reports that jernang rattans that produce high quality jernang resin are the types *D. didymophylla*, *D. draco*, *D. draconsellus*, *D. matleyi*, and *D. micracantha* (Nurwiyoto, 2021). Jernang resin has long been used by society and the world of trade as a raw material for dyes for various marble industries, ceramic industries, paper industries, and the medicine or pharmaceutical industry (Rahayu et al., 2012). Jernang resin in several areas, for example in the traditional community of the Anak Dalam tribe in Jambi, is used for shamanic practices, and also as medicine for wounds after childbirth, and medicine for toothache (Gupta et al., 2007). Furthermore, jernang resin is used by the community as a wound healer, anti-bacterial, stomach medicine, even as an anti-tumor and antioxidant (Yetty et al., 2013).

The analysis of genetic diversity within and among populations could be made by using genetic markers, such as random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) method. It is used to study the genetic variation within species, to determine the relationship between closely related species and genotypes within species, and to study the clonal structure (Asra et al., 2018). Gender identification of seedlings at the juvenile stage prior to plantation could help to revolutionize its future cultivation, as well as to investigate the sex determining mechanism of dioecious populations. An X/Y chromosome sex determination system has been described in a heteromorphic chromosome pair in staminate genotypes. The total and relative length of the Y-chromosome surpasses X-chromosome size. The development of sex-linked nucleic acid sequence makes up a vast portion of the population, which suggests that the sex is likely determined genetically (Wang et al., 2018).

To determine whether different species share an ancestral sex-determining system, the distribution of dioecy in phylogenies should therefore be supplemented by testing whether the sex-determining genes (or genome regions) are homologous. Alternatively, widely different ages should be excluded by estimating the times when suppressed recombination evolved. Species with X-autosome balance systems, rather than actively male-determining Y-linked regions, in *R. acetosa* and two species in the family Cannabaceae, *Cannabis sativa* and *Humulus lupulus*, also probably changed from ancestral XY systems (Charlesworth, 2016). The gender of the Jernang (*Daemonorops draco*) is determined by the structure of the inflorescence. This can only be determined after the plant flowers for the first time, namely after entering the reproductive phase at the age of 4-5 years. Male inflorescences of male individuals only have male flowers, while female inflorescences of female individuals have fertile female flowers and sterile male flowers. Sex ratio analysis shows that the sex expression of Jernang is most likely influenced by habitat conditions (Asra et al., 2012). Study of Asra et al. (2012) saying that the male Jernang population in Mandiangin has a greater number of stems (27.12) compared to female individuals (26.92). This means that male individuals grow faster than female individuals.

The success of a conservation program depends on the genetic diversity information of both within and between populations. The data on the genetic diversity of a plant is very important, because the genetic variation affect its existence in the natural population. Those plants with high genetic diversity could easily adapt to environmental changes . One method that could be used for this sex determination are ISSR and PCR. To determine the sex of the plants, it used ISSR and PCR method to determine it. The use of cytological analysis of X and Y chromosomes is possible only in some hop varieties. An use of molecular methods for marker-assisted selection (MAS) in large numbers of plants provides a means for rapid and reliable identification of agricultural important traits in F1 progenies (Patzak et al., 2002). ISSR (Inter Simple Sequence Repeat) markers are some of the most useful markers used in investigating the clonal diversity and population genetic structure. As a PCR-based marker, the ISSR marker has several advantages over others. The binding of ISSR primers is directed by simple sequence repeat, unlike the SSR marker that does not need prior knowledge of the target sequence on. In addition, the target sequences are very abundant throughout the ISSR eukaryotic genome and evolve rapidly. As a consequence, ISSR markers generate a large number of polymorphic fragments per primer (Asra et al., 2014). The ISSR marker has a high degree of reproducibility over RAPD markers, less costly use and the absence to use radioactivity in AFLP markers. Furthermore, it is used to observe genetic diversity, phylogenetic studies, gene tagging, genome mapping, and observe the evolution of various species. ISSR marker analyzes the genetic stability of various in vitro crops (Harahap et al., 2021).

Inter simple sequence repeat (ISSR) molecular markers are molecular markers that are generally used to study genetic diversity, phylogeny, gene tagging, genome mapping and evolutionary biology in various plants (Bani et al., 2017). ISSR has been widely used to assess plant genetic diversity, genetic stability, and the identification and screening of mutant plants. The advantage of this technique is that the designed microsatellite sequences are randomly distributed in the plant, deletions/duplications at binding sites can be used with ISSR primers, and multiple motifs can be detected simultaneously with high reliability and reproducibility, making it particularly suitable for the analysis of many mutants with limited genetic variation (Y. Li et al., 2023). The entire ISSR profile in the form of a collection of DNA bands is considered a putative locus and is a DNA fingerprint of the accession. The entire band profile resulting from ISSR primer amplification is the DNA fingerprint of each variety/accession. Observation of the DNA band patterns resulting from amplification shows different DNA profiles. This difference is caused by differences in the nucleotide sequences of the four primers used, causing the attachment of the primers along the sample's genomic DNA to also be different. The band produced after DNA amplification by PCR is very dependent on the primer part recognizing its complementary region on the DNA template used. The more attachment sites the primers use, the greater the number of DNA bands produced. Genetic diversity occurs due to segregation and gene interactions. Because ISSR and RAPD are markers that use random primers, the bands resulting from the amplification process are DNA fragments in the genome that are random in nature, either originating from coding or non-coding regions, in other words, there is diversity in both types of regions (Kusumadewi & Naiola, 2013).

In natural populations, it is possible that multiple sexual morphs are observed in a variety of flowering plants. Sexual morphs of higher plants are determined by the joint effects of sex chromosomes, sex related genes, phytohormone, and environmental influence. Sex-related genes in plants include sex-determining genes and sex differentiation genes. Sex-determining genes trigger the initiation of the development of the alternate sexual organs, while sex differentiation genes express afterward and are differentially expressed in different tissues, organs, and individuals, resulting in formation of flowers of different sexes (W. Li et al., 2023). Over the past decade, the sex-determination of flowering plants by a molecular mechanism was always an attractive research field, and a number of achievements have been made in dioecious plants. At present, morphologically distinctive sex chromosomes have been found in 13 plant species, of which the sex determination mechanism can be divided into 2 groups: the X-to-autosome ratio and the active Y-system (Sun et al., 2014).

The use of DNA sequences to identify organisms has been proposed as a more efficient approach than traditional taxonomic practices. Plants have relatively little sequence variation in their mitochondrial DNA, perhaps because of hybridization and introgression. A chloroplast gene such as matK (maturase K) or a nuclear gene such as ITS (Internal Transcribed Spacer) may be an effective target for barcoding in plants (Kress et al., 2005). Kress et al. (2005) have demonstrated the effectiveness of “DNA barcoding” in angiosperms using nrDNA and non-coding cpDNA sequences (Ali et al., 2015) .

According to data collected from the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List for 2022, more than 420,000 plant species exist around the world, yet a subset of them can be identified by traditional taxonomy based on morphological structures, namely, on the phenotypic characteristics of individual organisms. DNA barcodes are standardized sequences of DNA, ideally unique, from the genome either of the organism or from its organelles, with a length between 400 and 800 base pairs, that is used to identify/classify an organismal group following amplification, sequencing, and comparison with a reference database containing the relevant sequences from different species. DNA barcoding can also be used for the preservation of rare endemic and endangered species and, in general, for the research of evolution, ecology, and conservation of plants, especially since biodiversity has been threatened by anthropogenic activity, pollution, deforestation, and resource extraction (Letsiou et al., 2024).

Daemonorops draco have a lot of benefits, so that many people wants to cultivate it. To cultivating Rattan Jernang, it must be known what is the sex from the seed. One method that could be used to determine the sex are using ISSR and PCR method. By knowing the sex, it will make the planting of the seed of Rattan Jernang easier, and could be known the sex since it become a seed. After knowing the specific band of the sex, DNA barcoding could be used to save the specific band, and make it easier to identifying and could be uploaded to some websites, such as NCBI.

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